

Deliverable 2.10

**Final report on WP2 and draft
version of peer-reviewed
publication**

Workpackage 2

Responsible Partner: 36-INSA, 2-AGES

Contributing partners: 7-SZU, 14-UT, 23-UoS,
25-NUIG, 33-NVI

D-JRP15-FED-AMRWP2.10

FINAL REPORT ON WP2 AND DRAFT VERSION OF PEER-REVIEWED PUBLICATION

Description of action

The deliverable D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.10 (in the project proposal absent) consists of a brief summary of WP2 activities performed in the three years of the project (Y3, Y4 and Y5) and was intended to be established jointly with all tasks: WP2-T1, WP2-T2, WP2-T3, WP2-T3-ST1, WP2-T3-ST2, WP2-T3.2, WP2-T4, , WP2-T5, , WP2-T6 and WP2-T7.

WP2 aims at determining the naturally occurring Antimicrobial Resistance genes (ARG) background load and the microbial biodiversity in the tested environmental compartments (see Deliverable 2.1, Annex 1 for more information) through the following tasks:

- WP2-T1** Assemble list of sampling compartments and points. Determination of test areas representative for the European regions (North, West, East, South).
- WP2-T2** Establish common protocol for sampling and data analyses to facilitate comparability of the results between European test areas (North, West, East, South) and local sampling locations.
- WP2-T3** Assess microbial and ARG diversity with NGS in selected test environments, compare between ecosystems, characterization of cultivable environmental bacteria on complete nutrient and minimal media
 - WP2-T3.1** Shotgun sequencing and bioinformatic analyses of AMR genes and MGEs
 - WP2-T3.2** Gene enrichment with gene capture probes
- WP2-T4** Quantification of clinically relevant ARG tested by qPCR and or qPCR arrays
- WP2-T5** Identify naturally transformable bacterial species in tested compartments (NGS)
- WP2-T6** Asses clonal/lineage diversity in selected ARB species
- WP2-T7** Isolation and assessment of the quantity, diversity and stability of free extracellular ARG encoding DNA in tested environments, seq. Comparison

Description of the deliverable

Overall, WP2 aimed to answer four main questions: which ARGs and how many of them are present in each compartment, and which and how many bacteria are present in the compartments. The tasks below have been answering these questions through a large amount of results obtained derived from the sequencing (16S, gene enrichment, WGS).

In task **WP2-T1**, the countries involved in the WP2 sampling elaborated first a list of sampling compartments and points. Sample collectors integrated four EU regions: East (Czech Republic, Poland), West (Austria, Ireland and Great Britain), North (Estonia and Norway), and South (Portugal). In addition, a sample timeline by collectors, a sample distribution list, and the transportation and conservation requirements for the samples was generated by WP2. Unique identifiers by compartment and time point were given to all samples. The outcome of this task is summarized in D-

JRP15- FED-AMR–WP2.1 and the corresponding annexes.

In task **WP2-T2**, common protocols for the collection of different sample types, their processing and cultivation, DNA extraction (extracellular and total), antimicrobial susceptibility testing, whole genome sequencing and metagenomics sequence analysis, were generated by WP2. They supported the harmonization of testing procedures and enhanced comparability of the results obtained from different regions of Europe. The outcome of this task is also summarized in D-JRP15- FED-AMR–WP2.1 and the corresponding annexes.

In the task **WP2-T3**, regarding the characterization of cultivable bacteria by WGS-based typing, more than 300 animal and environmental bacterial isolates belonging to clinically-relevant species, such as *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecium* and *Enterococcus faecalis* were obtained after sample cultivation by the six participating countries. Also, nearly 200 strains belonging to other bacterial species, mostly environmental, were gathered by the partners. The first 300 strains were tested for antimicrobial susceptibility and paired-end sequenced was carried out on Illumina devices at each institute. Afterwards, raw genome sequences (FASTQ) were forwarded to 2-AGES for genome assembly, species re-identification, species-specific assessment of the genetic relatedness by core genome MLST using publicly available schemes, extraction of the sequence types of the classical MLSTs, and extraction of ARGs and virulence genes using CARD and VFDB databases, respectively. Afterwards, the assemblies (FASTA) were shared with 33-NVI for further analyses. The Mobile Element Finder was used to identify mobile genetic elements (MGE). Also, an in-house pipeline (Ellipsis (<https://github.com/NorwegianVeterinaryInstitute/Ellipsis>)) was used for detection of plasmid replicons and for re-extraction of ARGs and VGs in all FASTA files; ARGs were determined using ResFinder, virulence genes using VirulenceFinder, and plasmid replicons using PlasmidFinder and mob-suite. The analysis of associations between ARGs and the compartments and countries in which the respective strains were isolated was performed. The identified MGE also provide information about the possible dissemination via horizontal gene transfer of ARGs and VGs between clones of the same or different species, countries and compartments.

cgMLST-based analysis showed intra-country isolate clusters of the same species, but no multi-country cluster was detected. However, for several strains, the same ST was detected in more than one country, especially among the *E. coli* isolates. In all countries, isolates retrieved from wastewater, pig manure and pigs were those carrying more ARGs, including extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBL), but also ARGs associated to antimicrobials usually used in animal husbandry such as aminoglycosides, tetracyclines or sulfonamides.

Two manuscripts have been already published on phenotypical and WGS-based characterization of 89 environmental bacteria from Austria belonging to clinically-relevant species. As for Portugal, ARG in isolates from the *Enterobacter cloacae* complex related with non-susceptibility to β -lactams, quinolones, fosfomycin and macrolides as well as several MGEs were identified. Phylogenetic analysis identified two main clusters with closely related strains from different compartments. Almost all isolates were non-susceptible to colistin and resistant to at least one carbapenem due to carbapenemase production, and were obtained from three compartments (river water, sludge, and effluent from a stabilization pond). These results were presented at ECCMID 2022 and were part of an MSc thesis defended and published in 2022. Results from the WGS-based characterization and the phenotypical tests carried out by Czech Republic, UK, Estonia, Ireland and Portugal (other species different from *E. cloacae*) have potential titles for the future manuscripts that will be drafted with those results.

Regarding the assesment of microbial and ARG diversity with NGS in the selected test environments (metagenomics), the FED-AMR partners agreed on the evaluation and comparison of ARGs using a novel methodology based on gene capture probes (equivalent to gene enrichment, see subtask **WP2-T3-ST2** for more information). This methodology allowed us to analyse the ARGs and MGEs, and dispense with both conventional shotgun metagenomics (this subtask **WP2-T3-ST1**) and qPCR (task WP2-T4) for the collected samples.

To ensure that target enrichment could be used instead of PCR and conventional shotgun metagenomics to analyze all the exDNA and/or total DNA obtained from the WP2 samples, we conducted a small pilot experiment comparing the results obtained for a pair of samples with shotgun metagenomics (subtask **WP2-T3-ST2**) and target enrichment. As target enrichment showed superiority in detecting more ARGs, especially in the exDNA, the FED-AMR Supervisory Board agreed on the increased sensitivity and novelty of the use of target enrichment exclusively as a better approach to detect and quantify ARGs in the different compartments and EU countries.

Afterwards we performed the DNA extraction (exDNA and/or total DNA) and quality control of all samples within WP2 that were further enriched and sequenced. Results involved the generation of two large datasets grouping all the ARGs obtained in each of the samples by marker class and mechanism of resistance. These two large datasets included two different approaches to analyse gene enrichment data: 1) the one offered by the company ARES Genetics and 2) the one described by Lanza *et al.* (2015). WP2 considered the second approach as the best option, since it had been previously published and showing the benefit. Intensive data cleaning had been carried out in both cases, for both 16S and AMR data. Regarding AMR, we encountered some irregularities in the results provided by Ares Genetics (that did metagenomics for all the consortium), as did not contain the annotation of the information in the final format for a direct analysis, so it took more time (e.g. the ARG names, particularly regarding their classification into different AMR groups, which necessitated a manual revision of the ARGs names and classification). Statistical analyses have been completed using several R packages. These include evaluation of the ARGs diversity, among others, in each of the samples, DNA types (extracellular vs. total), compartments and countries. We are drafting a first paper including the wildlife results for both exDNA and total DNA from samples collected in Austria, Ireland and Portugal, which can also be considered a martyr document from where we will be able to correct and fine-tune the analysis and writing of the papers on the other compartments, related to metagenomics.

Regarding the quantification of clinically relevant ARG tested by qPCR and or qPCR arrays (**WP2-T4**), as explained in the report of Year 3, the detection of ARG through qPCRs was eliminated from the project. The Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB) contributed to this decision-making process. However, the quantification of relevant ARGs in the analysed compartments was performed, inferring from the number of reads that cover each detected ARG.

To identify naturally transformable bacteria in the compartments tested (**WP2-T5**), a query database containing bacterial species proven to be able to take up extracellular DNA under naturally occurring environmental conditions was generated. For this purpose, a literature search for naturally competent bacteria covering the years from 1994 to 2021 was performed using defined search strings, with PubMed and SCOPUS as reference databases. Only hits describing the development of competence in bacteria under physiological conditions were eligible for entering the query database. The bacterial species names retrieved from literature were annotated and the appropriate phylogenetic levels were allocated according to the taxonomic classification system as laid down in SILVA 138.1. For the annotation and classification of 16S NGS data generated in the frame of the project the same version of SILVA database was employed. The resulting collection of observed bacterial species in FED-AMR samples was used as the searched database. This search database was checked for the presence of bacteria sampled in the query database using the level “genus” as qualifier. The research questions were: 1. Are naturally transformable bacteria present in FED-AMR isolates? 2. If yes, in which compartments? 3. Which competent bacteria are to be found in these compartments?

The query database contained 171 entries (= bacterial species) with empirically obtained evidence for their natural transformability. The searched database contained the 16S sequence information of 488 samples and 5763 different bacterial species. Naturally transformable bacteria were identified in almost all samples (except for a sample from soil and from a farmer – both of exDNA as sample type), in all sample types and environmental compartments. The overall most prevalent taxons encountered in FED-AMR samples were *Pseudomonads* and *Sphingomonads*. *Lactobacilli* were found in a significantly lower number of samples, but showed highly abundant genus-specific sequence reads.

Samples from wildlife (exDNA), farmers (ex/total DNA) and crops (ex/total DNA) carried the lowest abundance of competent bacteria. The highest loads with competent bacteria could be observed in feed (exDNA), groundwater (total DNA) and field drainage (total DNA). We can conclude that bacteria known to be able to take up extracellular DNA are present in all environmental compartments and may serve as receptor for ARG encoded on free exDNA. The detailed statistical evaluation of the obtained results focusing on country-specific comparisons and the comparison with *in silico* alignment studies based upon comEC homologies complete this task.

In the original task **WP2-T6**, phylogenetic trees using 16S amplicon sequencing and the shotgun, sequencing data were intended. However, since the number of samples that the consortium analysed was significantly higher than the initially planned, the methodological approach was modified and no phylogenetic analysis was done using the raw data (FASTQ). See deliverable D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.6 for additional information.

Really, as well as the resistome referred above, the microbial biodiversity in the tested environmental compartments from all partners was evaluated by characterising all 16S V1-V9 regions through 16S rRNA metagenomics and target gene enrichment. Thus, after cleaning up the data, all OTUs (Operational Taxonomic Units) with no reads, and correcting some errors we ended up with 573646 OTUs in 476 samples. We then proceeded to create a Phyloseq (R package) object using the available data in the literature (McMurdie & Holmes, 2013).

We divided the samples into 11 compartments: Crop – crops harvested in the agricultural fields; Feed – proceed feeds for animal consumption; Farmers – faeces samples from farmers; Pigs_Barn – faeces from farm pigs; Manure – faeces of pigs and other organic material used to fertilize the soil; Wild_animals – faeces samples of wild animals like deal, hares, but also sheep and goat; Soil_Fs_Ms_Ctrl_Bline – soil samples from forests, meadows and agricultural fields before being cultivated or fertilized; Soil_field_noMan – soil samples from agricultural fields fertilized without the use of manure; Soil_field_Man – soil samples from agricultural fields fertilized with of manure; water_DRG – water samples from drainage, river and ground water; water_WTP – water samples from waste treatment plants.

Overall, water_DRG is the only compartment exclusively with samples that did not pass the quality control. If we separate the data sample type we will have 232 samples and 1725 genera for extracellular DNA samples and 223 samples and 1810 genera in total DNA samples. Phyla in extracellular and total DNA samples, are dominated by *Proteobacteria* and *Firmicutes*. Most of the Phyla are present in both extracellular and total DNA samples. *Acidobacteriota*, *Chloflexi* and *Gemmatimonadota* have higher reads in soil samples while *Bacteroidota* and *Firmicutes* have higher reads in farmers, pigs, manure and wild animals samples. Concerning alpha diversity, we explored the data with and without rarefaction (a procedure commonly used in microbial diversity analysis, but which may lead to loss of data). Our samples present high variability in the number of reads: 16 to the sample with least reads and 939820 for the sample with most reads. 72449 and 90698 for median and mean respectfully. Pielou's evenness index does not seem to be greatly affected by the total number of reads in each sample, both Chao1 and Shannon are. According to the rarefaction curves we identified that most of the samples approach the asymptote, which signalled that sampling depth was enough to capture the diversity in the sampled populations. The compartments that are significantly different from each other in terms of alpha diversity were determined both in the extracellular and total DNA samples. Most of the compartments were significantly different. From a total of 55 possible comparisons between compartments, we have 42 agreements extracellular and total DNA samples when rarefication was used and 45 agreements when rarefication was not used. This suggest that there are some punctual differences concerning alpha diversity between the extracellular and total DNA. Note that soil samples from forests, meadows, controls and baselines are significantly different than the other soil samples in extracellular DNA, but not in total DNA. In both types of samples, soil with and without manure did not present significant differences, which may be due to a history of exposure to manure in the preceding years (ARG "memory effect").

To perform ordination analysis we used CLR (centered log ratio) transformation that allowed us to use Aitchison distance. In both extracellular and total DNA samples PC1 separate soil samples from everything else, PC2 and PC3 separate the other compartments. The first three principal components explain 41.6%, 8.9% and 4.0% of the data variability in extracellular DNA samples and 45.2%, 7.3% and 5.3% in total DNA samples. PC2 and PC3 separate crops, feeds and water samples from farmers, pigs and manure, with wild animals samples bridging these two clusters. We used multiple differential abundance methods to help ensure robust biological interpretations and we choose ALCOM-BC, ALDEx2 and the Wilcoxon test with CLR transformation. Respective analysis was performed for the other compartments.

Regarding OTU's in both extracellular and total DNA samples, the compartments are divided into two main groups that separate the soil samples from everything else, as in the ordination analysis. The remaining samples are further divided into two groups: one with the mammals, another with the crops, feeds and water_DRG. Water_WTP and manure seem not to cluster with any other compartment. Concerning the separation for the OUT's we see that there are separations, which are common to the extracellular and total DNA and others that are specific. In both types of samples, we note large OUT's clusters exclusive from soil, others that are exclusive from manure and others exclusive for water_WTP. Following the group order in the dendrogram for the OUT's in the total DNA samples, we have a first cluster shared by mammals and manure, another that is shared by mammals, water_WTP, manure and soil samples. These are followed by a cluster shared by every compartment. For other clusters it is difficult to assign a characteristic. The total DNA samples seem to have a cluster that is shared by wild_animals, crops, feeds and soil samples that is not as evident in the extracellular DNA heatmap.

Overall, the data suggest: A) Separation between three groups: 1) soil; 2) crops, feeds and drinking water; 3) farmers, pigs, wild animals, manure and waste water. B) No significant difference was detected between soil in fields with and without manure. C) Differences were detected between extracellular and total DNA samples in: farmers, feeds and soil. D) Very few samples of water that also did not pass quality control. This analysis may already show a smaller shifting between the microorganisms found globally in the compartments of these three groups, suggesting a greater (or more complex) interplay between the microorganisms of the compartments that correspond to farmers, pigs, wild animals, manure and wastewater.

To isolate and assess quantity, diversity and stability of free extracellular ARG encoding DNA in the tested environments (**WP2-T7**), the extracted extracellular free DNA from all the collected samples was used according to the generated protocols based on previous literature available. Gene enrichment was performed as described in WP2-T3.

We first evaluated the quality of the extracted total and extracellular free DNA. Qubit measurements of double stranded DNA were done for all the samples. Further quality assessments of the samples were done as explained in D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.6. In addition, we removed from the analysis all those genes with a coverage below 0.5. For a total of 475 samples 7252 different ARGs were detected.

Most samples presented good amount of Transcripts Per Kilobase Million (TPMs). Only 21 out of 475 had an insufficient number of reads. TPMs in the samples by country were analysed. Overall, the number of TPMs for the exDNA was similar to that of the total DNA and the ARGs with the highest TPM sums corresponded to the tetracycline ARG tetW, which was present in 343 samples, and mutations in ribosomal subunits. As for the number of ARGs in each compartment, there was variations among compartments, DNA type and countries.

After this overview on ARGs quantity and diversity the more complex statistical analyses is clarifying the differences between compartments, countries and DNA type regarding ARGs, their antibiotic class and resistance mechanism.

All ARG results provided by Ares Genetics were analyzed and grouped according to AMR mechanisms, as follows: antibiotic inactivation, target alteration (replacement and alteration), target protection and

efflux impermeability; in the group called 'others' we have mainly resistance genes to heavy metals and biocides, as well as virulence genes (adherence, motility, chemotaxis, etc). The first specific analysis on ARG concerns the wildlife compartment; we found that the ARGs obtained in samples from this compartment confer resistance to about 30 antibiotic classes, where the most prevalent were mainly the following classes (in descending order): β -lactams, tetracyclines, aminoglycosides and fluoroquinolones. Among β -lactams the prevalent resistance mechanism was the β -lactamase production [mostly class A β -lactamases, including ESBLs (e.g. encoded by *bla_{CfXA}*), class C, namely PMA β (plasmid-mediated AmpC β -lactamases; e.g. encoded by *bla_{CMY}*, *bla_{ACT}*, *bla_{ACC}*, *bla_{MIR}*, *bla_{DHA}*, *bla_{ADC}*), and class D β -lactamases, such as carbapenemases (e.g. encoded by *bla_{OXA-types}*)]. In the same compartment, we identified genes encoding resistance to aminoglycosides through the action of aminoglycoside phosphotransferase (e.g. *aph(2'')-IIa*, *aph(3')-Ia*, *aph(3'')-Ib*), and 11 ARG-types conferring resistance to fluoroquinolones, which included episomal (such as *qnrB*, *qnrD*, *qnrE*) and chromosomal (*oqxA*, *gyrA*, *gyrB*) mutated gene variants. We also identified resistance to heavy metals, such as (more prevalent in descending order) to copper, mercury, tellurium, arsenic, nickel-cobalt, chromium and silver.

AMR data in our study (including those from metagenomics) are not thought to be a direct result of antimicrobial drug use, because 'globally' there is no direct linkage of AMR across the various compartments and countries associated with the antibiotics from the classes identified in WP4, therefore, there will be other risk factors.

Comparison of microbial and antimicrobial resistance gene diversity across ecosystems and along ecosystem boundaries, as well as discussion of results are included in the **manuscripts under preparation**, under the following titles:

- Microbial composition and ARGs diversity in wild mammals of Portugal, Austria and Ireland (WP2).
- Assessing the microbial composition and ARGs diversity in Europe in different compartments along the feed/food chain.
- Tackling the dissemination of ARGs between compartments of the feed/food chain with target enrichment.
- Prevalence of naturally competent bacteria in European Agroecosystems (and their relevance in AMR dissemination).
- Correlation analysis reveals strong association of free extracellular ARGs with certain trace elements in environmental compartments of the food/feed chain.

All of these manuscripts, along **with the following publications, provide the answers to questions planned for WP2:**

- Draft Genome Sequence of a Multidrug-Resistant Escherichia coli Sequence Type 1193 Pandemic Clone Isolated from Wastewater in Austria. Microbiology Resource Announcements DOI: 10.1128/MRA.00762-21 <https://zenodo.org/record/5770120#.YeZ1rd8xl4F>
- Characterizing Antimicrobial Resistance in Clinically Relevant Bacteria Isolated at the Human/Animal/Environment Interface Using Whole-Genome Sequencing in Austria. Journal International Journal of Molecular Sciences. Doi: 10.3390/ijms231911276 <https://zenodo.org/record/7446455#.Y5xQ-FGZND8>
- Coelho, Rodrigo. Characterization of Antibiotic Resistance in Strains Isolated from Different Environmental Reservoirs [Caracterização da Resistência aos Antibióticos em estirpes isoladas de diferentes reservatórios ambientais]. Master thesis, 2022. <http://hdl.handle.net/10451/53801>

Deliverables released (all):

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1 List of sampling compartments, points and European test areas and harmonized protocols in alignment with EFFORT project protocols available in data repository (T2.1, T2.2)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5081756>

- D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.2 Preliminary data collection on ARG prevalence and ARG background load in the compartments analysed so far (T2.4)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5078064>
- D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.3 Annual report Y3 (WP2)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5078149>
- D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.4: Determination of naturally transformable bacteria in tested environmental compartments (T2.5)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7446361>
- D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.5: Shotgun sequencing: ARG diversity in tested environmental compartments (T2.3.1)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5726732>
- D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.6: 16S metagenomics results: Microbial biodiversity and phylogenetic relationships of ARBs over ecosystem boundaries (T2.3, T2.6)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7057188>
- D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.7: Quantity and stability of free extracellular DNA observed in environmental compartments tested so far (T2.7)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7547822>
- D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.8: Annual report for Y4 (WP2)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7057332>
- D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.9: ARG dynamics in an agricultural testing area: Response of ARG concentrations according to different fertilisation techniques and crops over an annual growth period (WP2)
- D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.10: Final report on WP2 and draft version of peer-reviewed publication (WP2)

Milestones released (all):

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-07 List of sampling compartments, points and European test areas available. Harmonized protocols for sample collection + transportation, DNA extraction, qPCR, metagenomics, shotgun sequencing, gene capture and bioinformatics and statistical analysis of sequence data available. Alignment with EFFORT project protocols (T2.1, T2.2).

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-08: Start of annual field study (i.e. sampling campaign, sample collection) (T2.3).

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-09: Start of DNA isolations and cultivation of ARB strains (immediately after reception of the first environmental samples) (T2.3, T2.7).

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-11: Start collecting data for annual report (WP2).

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-12: Starting preparations for gene capture probe approach (T2.3.2).

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-13: Finishing annual report (WP2).

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-15: Stop: field sampling campaign (T2.3), DNA isolations (T2.7).

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-16: Starting 16S metagenome analysis of obtained DNA isolates. Batch format (T2.3).

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-17: Start: Determination of naturally transformable bacteria (T2.5).

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-19: Finalizing determination of transformable bacteria (T2.5).

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-20: Start: Assessment of clonal/lineage diversity of ARB (T2.6).

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-21: Finalizing 16S metagenome analysis of obtained DNA isolates (T2.3).

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-22: Finalizing assessment of clonal/lineage diversity of ARB (T2.6).

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-23: Finalizing shot gun sequencing and bioinformatics and statistical analysis of NGS data (T2.3.1, T3.2.2, T2.3).

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-24: Delivery of final annual report on WP2 + draft version of peer reviewed paper (WP2).

Milestones 'Not applicable':

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-10: Start of performing qPCRs (T2.4): Not applicable, as qPCR were replaced by Ares genetics services.

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-14: Starting preparations for shotgun sequencing (T2.3.1): Not applicable, as Shotgun Metagenomics was replaced for target enrichment (see Task 2.3.1).

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-18: Finalizing ARG qPCRs (T2.4). Not applicable: qPCRs were replaced by target enrichment.

Project self-assessment: In WP2, the prior limited knowledge on free exDNA posed consequently diverse methodological challenges, such as the generation and validation of novel protocols for extraction of this DNA fraction. Despite the low exDNA concentrations obtained for some of the samples, the quality of the sequencing data exceeded our expectation. There is nevertheless room for improvement in the future with respect to the exDNA extraction protocols. Indeed, the time planned in the project proposal for the development of these protocols, specific to each of the compartments, was not realistic enough. Regarding target enrichment, this new approach has undoubtedly been the method that has allowed us to obtain harmonized AMR data for all participating countries in shorter time and with excellent results. Although there are still questions to be answered, we consider that all the initial objectives for this WP have been met. We have generated a unique dataset containing comprehensive information, from exDNA and tDNA, on microbial biodiversity (16S rDNA) and ARGs present in different compartments along the food/feed chain and in one-year crop growing season. Up to our knowledge, there are no studies integrating so many compartments that use target enrichment to detect ARGs in exDNA. The large datasets obtained here together with the associated metadata make our results a unique resource that will be available to other researchers and from which further studies can be performed.

Impact from WP2 (some):

This WP2 will have the following scientific impacts:

Cross-sector communication of data contributing to the advancement of science, namely e.g.:

- By a study capitalized on advancements in high-throughput sequencing methods and analytical tools, as it provides the large scalability necessary to investigate bacterial communities, in a way to explore and mapping AMR in exDNA, either in human, animal, and environmental settings, and in several sample matrices.
- By sampling campaigns that provided basic information for establishing ARG monitoring in environmental compartments, which is recommended by EFSA and has the potential to become compulsory for EU MS.
- By using the true concept of One Health, namely with an important environmental component

(farmers, pigs, wild animals, manure, air of pig barns, feeds, crops, soil, water).

At a societal, policy-maker and economic impact:

- Impactful research that adds value to an European, national and international level.
- Decisive for assessing the potential of exDNA to serve as a high-risk source of resistance determinants in agricultural soils and along the food/feed chain.
- Impact on strategies to improve and/or upgrade wastewater treatment plants, as it is decisive for WWTP engineers to know if they have to design devices that only kill bacteria or if strategies to eliminate bacterial DNA from the waste streams would have to be applied.
- As reliable and accurate surveillance is fundamental to characterize the risk of AMR in a given region, the results obtained show how essential it is to track the spread of specific ARGs geographically and over time, identify new ARGs and support preventive measures and interventions against AMR pathogens.

In the **Annex 1** to this deliverable are the WP2 publications available.